

Report on the VETNET research workshop
during the third EU Vocational Skills Week in Vienna, 07.11.2018

Vocational education and training across the lifespan

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Introduction

VETNET mission

The Vocational Education and Training Network VETNET is an open network, which welcomes contributions from all over the world as long as they are in line with the goals of VETNET.

VETNET is focusing on research and development in the field of initial, higher and continuing vocational education and training (VET) and learning across the life-span.

The goals of VETNET are to promote research on vocational education and training and to contribute its development by:

- fostering a high quality of research in the field of vocational education and training;
- exploring the relationship between research, policy and practice;
- stimulating the multidisciplinary discussion and dissemination of research results in the European research area and beyond through mutual learning;
- encouraging, establishing and maintaining cooperation between VET researchers and project partnerships in the European research area through, e.g., organising the VETNET programme at the ECER, Crossing Boundaries or Stockholm International Conference; developing international contacts; cooperating with other relevant conferences; publications or by producing electronic or other newsletters;
- maintaining the peer-reviewed VETNET journal IJRNET, the VETNET ECER proceedings and contributing to other international publications; maintaining the community website vetnetsite.org.

VETNET

- maintains a community website on vetnetsite.org;
- has an entry on the EERA website: <https://eera-ecer.de/networks/2-vocational-education-and-training-vetnet/>;
- has a project on [researchgate.net](https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training): <https://www.researchgate.net/project/IRNVET-VETNET-International-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training-VETNET-European-Research-Network-in-Vocational-Education-and-Training>;
- has a community on <https://zenodo.org/communities/vetnet/> to host the conference proceedings.

Aim and scope of the workshop

The topic of the researchers' workshop at the EU Vocational Skills Week 2018 in Vienna was: "Vocational education and training across the lifespan".

All participants contributed to the workshop with a short abstract on the topic "Vocational education and training across the lifespan" and a short bibliography.

Four presentations were selected as impetus presentations. These were short presentations by the authors to stimulate the discussion in the workshop. After the discussion, the presenters of the impetus presentations wrote short minutes on the discussion during the workshop. The impetus presentations and minutes are covered in this report.

Programme of the workshop

Introduction

- Dr Christof Nägele
Senior Researcher, University of Applied Sciences and Arts, Northwestern Switzerland
- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler
Professor, Institute Technology and Education, University of Bremen
- Mantas Sekmokas
Policy Officer, European Commission, DG Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion

Impetus Presentations

Lifelong learning and VET: towards understanding the influence of societal eco-systems on learning across the lifespan

- Dr Natalia (Natasha) Kersh
UCL Institute of Education, University of London
- Dr Karen Evans
Professor Emeritus, UCL Institute of Education, University of London

Apprenticeship Reform in France

- Eric Dumartin
Vice-President of Fongecif Île-de-France, Vice-President of IAE Paris I Panthéon Sorbonne

The VET Skills Cycle and the Formation of Construction Management Skills in Ireland

- Eoghan Ó Murchadha
Assistant Head of Department of Craft, Design, Construction and Apprenticeship, Dún Laoghaire Further Education Institute in Dublin

The Role of VET on the Inclusion of Marginalized Young People and Adult People from a Lifelong Perspective across the Lifespan

- Dr Patricia Olmos Rueda
Professor, Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB)
- Dr Fernando Marhuenda
Professor, University of Valencia

Outlook

- Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler & Dr Christof Nägele

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Biographies of Participants

Short biographies of the researchers participating at the Vocational Skills Week 2018.

Dr Vibe Aarkrog is an Associate Professor at the Danish School of Education, Aarhus University. Her research concerns vocational pedagogy and didactics with a focus on the interrelation of the school-based and workplace-based parts of the education and training.

Dr Giuditta Alessandrini is a full Professor of Social and Work Pedagogy at the Department of Education, Roma Tre University, Italy. She is the coordinator of the PhD School of pedagogy, and she is the director of Master HR Specialist and of the Centre for Research “CEFORC, Continuing training & Communication”. Her research interests include the field of adult training in organisations, the pedagogy of work, teacher and VET teacher education.

Dr James Avis is a Professor of Post-Compulsory Education and Training at the University of Huddersfield. His research interests lie in vocational education and training, post-secondary education and life-long learning. He has written extensively on the policy contextualisation of further education, having addressed curriculum issues, methodological questions, teacher professionalism, as well as the lived experience of teachers and learners.

Dr Magdolna Benke is a researcher of CHERD at the University of Debrecen, Hungary. Her research interests include the governance of VET, the role of social partners in VET, the regional dimension of VET, the role of VET in creating learning regions and learning communities, workplace learning.

Dr Harm J.A. Biemans is an Associate Professor at the Education and Learning Sciences group of Wageningen University & Research. His research concentrates on competence development of (future) professionals and design and effects of corresponding learning environments.

Dr Lorenzo Bonoli is a senior researcher and senior lecturer at the Swiss Federal Institute for Vocational Education and Training in Lausanne. His research interests include systemic issues and evolution of the Swiss VET system, international issues of VET, comparison of international VET systems, the epistemology of social sciences, discourse analysis.

Dr Nora Cechovsky is a research associate at the Institute of Business Education at the Vienna University of Economics and Business in Austria. Her research interests focus on initial vocational education and training, tax literacy, economic literacy, teaching methods in interpersonal skills development, teacher education and educational assessment.

Dr Trine Deichman-Sørensen is a Professor at the Department of Vocational Teacher Education at Oslo Metropolitan University, Norway. Her research interests include institutional change and educational reforms, curriculum studies, emergent occupations and knowledge practices, and interrelations between digital and analogical literacy.

Dr Ludger Deitmer is a senior researcher at the University of Bremen at the Institute of Technology and Education, ITB and lecturer at the study programme ‘Vocational Education’ he coordinates international research activities. His research interest covers forming innovative skills of vocational teachers, trainers and apprentices in different occupational domains.

Dr M'Hamed Dif is a senior associate researcher within BETA-Céreq Alsace at the University of Strasbourg, France. He is working in the following research areas: Lifelong learning and qualification systems, inclusion and VET-labour market relationships, competence assessment and validation of experiential learning, work identities and HRD, innovation, learning organisations and regions.

Eric Dumartin is an HR professional and a specialist of training funds in France as past president of the FPSPP (Fund of Securitization of professional path, 1,5 billion €) and now at vice-President du Fongecif Île-de-France, one of the major funds for reorientation. He is a school board member and vice president of IAE Paris I Panthéon Sorbonne. He has a broad

vision of the efficiency of French programs to develop training across the lifespan, mainly for lowest qualified employees.

Dr Karen Evans is an Emeritus Professor of Education in UCL Institute of Education, University of London and Honorary Professor in the Economic and Social Research Council LLAKES Centre for Learning and Life Chances. Her research interests include international and comparative studies of learning in life and work transitions throughout the life course; her most recent co-authored book is 'How Non-Permanent Workers Learn and Develop' 2018 (Routledge).

Dr Dr h.c. Benedicte Gendron is a Professor of University at the University of Montpellier III, in France. She was the Former Vice-President of the University in charge of VET and socio-economics affairs. As a Doctor in Economics and Doctor in psychology, her research interest is about Emotional Capital, focused on transversal skills and soft skills, precisely emotional competencies' developments and their impacts at micro, meso and macro levels as at work, in education, and on health and well-being, and on societal cohesion and creativity...

Dr Dr h.c. Michael Gessler is a Professor of Vocational and Professional Education and Training in Institute Technology and Education (ITB), University of Bremen, Germany. His research interests include international and comparative studies in VET, organisational development and cooperation between schools and companies, workprocess-oriented learning and instructional design.

Dr Christian Helms Jørgensen is a Professor mso, at Roskilde University in Denmark. His research covers adult education, comparative vocational education, school-to-work transitions, learning in working life, gender and education and students' drop-out from schools.

Dr Natasha Kersh is a Lecturer in Education, at the Department of Education, Practice and Society, UCL Institute of Education. Her research interests and publications relate to the study of VET in the UK and international contexts as well as comparative education, lifelong learning, and adult education.

Dr Andrea Laczik is a Research and Policy Manager at the Edge Foundation and a University Lecturer at the University of Oxford, Department of Education, UK. She is interested, for example, in professional and technical education (VET), skills development, employer engagement in education, transition from school to work/higher education and from higher education to employment. She is also interested in these areas in comparative and international (European) context.

Dr Johanna Lasonen is a Professor at the University of South Florida. She worked as a UNESCO Professor (Intercultural Education in workforce) in Finland. She has over 40 years as a K-12 teacher, a technical teacher educator, and a University Professor. She holds two doctoral degrees: Vocational and Technical Education, Virginia Tech; and Educational Sciences, University of Jyvaskyla, Finland. She has been a visiting scholar in many international universities and received many prestige research fundings. Her research has focused on the comparisons of education systems in different countries, immigrant integration with equity and access, efficiency of learning environments and work-based learning.

Dr Lorenz Lassnigg works as Senior Researcher at the Institute for Advanced Studies in Vienna, Austria. His research interests are about VET policies and governance and the development of lifelong learning, more recently he has started to work about social progress in education and the relationship of VET to democratic education.

Dr Junmin Li is a postdoctoral researcher at the Chair of Economics and Business Education at the University of Cologne, Germany. Her research focuses on international comparative vocational education and training, vocational school development and vocational program evaluation.

Dr Krista Loogma work in Tallinn University, Estonia as a Professor of vocational and professional education. Her competence areas are related to education sociology, including areas of education and labour market, education policy, research methodology.

Dr Fernando Marhuenda is Full University Professor at the Department of Didactics and School Organization at the University of Valencia, Spain. His research interests focus on vocational education and training, particularly workplace learning, transitions between education and work and vulnerability.

Dr Jörg Markowitsch is Senior Partner at 3s Unternehmensberatung GmbH in Vienna which he founded in 2001. He holds a Doctoral Degree in Humanities and a Master degree in Science and Technology. His areas of research include Comparative Research in Vocational Education and Training (VET); European Educational Policy; firm-based training; acquisition of competences; skill taxonomies; skills forecasting.

Dr Mónica Moso-Diez is the Head of the Research and Innovation Centre at the Bankia Foundation for Dual Training, Spain. Her research interests include investigation of VET public policy making, public policies for research, development and innovation policies, and VET and business innovation strategies.

Dr Christof Nägele is a senior researcher at the Centre for Learning and Socialisation, Institute for Research and Development, School of Education at the University of Applied Sciences and Arts Northwestern Switzerland. His research interests focus on vocational orientation, career choice of young people, learning and career development of adult workers, individual, group level and structural resources in vocational education and training.

Dr Paolo Nardi is Director of Cometa Research Centre on Education and Welfare based on the Cometa VET school (Como, IT) and coordinator of the UNEVOC Centre of Excellence for Italy. He is Fellow at PlusValue and Assistant Editor of the Journal of Economics and Policy of Energy and the Environment. His research interests are focused on VET policy analysis and evaluation, didactic innovation, social innovation and community development.

Dr Petri Nokelainen is a Professor of Engineering Pedagogy at the Laboratory of Industrial and Information management at the Tampere University of Technology, Finland. His research interests include investigation of professional growth, development of professional and vocational excellence, learning environments, educational technology applications and applied multivariate and Bayesian methods.

Dr des Eoghan Ó Murchadha is Assistant Head of Dept of Craft, Design, Construction and Apprenticeship in Dún Laoghaire Further Education Institute in Dublin, Ireland. With 20 years' experience teaching apprentices, he is putting his expertise to use in Doctoral research at the Dublin Institute of Technology. His research field examines mechanisms to stabilise apprenticeship engagement by employers during periods of economic uncertainty.

Dr Patricia Olmos is a Professor in the Department of Applied Pedagogy at the Autonomous University of Barcelona (UAB), Spain. Her research interests are focussed on inclusive education, social and labour inclusion, vulnerable groups, basic and initial VET, early school leaving, diversity, tutoring action, guidance processes and training for improving employability and key competencies.

Dr Jeroen Onstenk is Professor emeritus of Pedagogical Practice at Inholland University of Applied Science. His research interests include Teacher Training, Vet, lifelong learning and more specifically Work Based Learning. He is focussing on the intricate relations between working, learning and organisational innovation and the acquisition of key competencies, in vocational education and apprenticeships as well as during career.

Dr Matthias Pilz is a Professor of Economics and Business Education at the University of Cologne and Director of the German Research Center for Comparative Vocational Education and Training. His research interests are in international comparative research in VET, transitions from education to employment, and teaching and learning.

Dr Tomasz Rachwał is a Head of the Department of Entrepreneurship and Spatial Management at the Pedagogical University of Cracow, Poland. He is also the Rector's Proxy for Entrepreneurship and head of the team of experts on developing a core (national) curriculum of entrepreneurship for general and vocational schools, as well as the author of many textbooks on

entrepreneurship and economic geography for various types of schools. He carried out projects in the field of competence development in vocational and prevocational education as well as on vocational career guidance. His research interests include goals, content and methods of entrepreneurship and geographic education as well as transformation of the spatial and branch structure of industry.

Dr Justin Rami is Director of Dublin City University's Further Education and Training Research Centre (FETRC). He is lecturer and researcher in the School of Policy & Practice, and is currently the Associate Dean for Teaching & Learning in DCU's Institute of Education in Dublin. Dr Rami has 15 years' experience researching and publishing in the areas of VET and FET in Ireland and beyond.

Heta Rintala is a PhD student in the Tampere University of Technology, Finland. Her research interests include VET systems, work-based learning and workplace learning.

Dr Barbara E. Stalder is a Professor at the Institute of Upper Secondary Education at Bern University of Teacher Education, Switzerland. Her research focuses on student engagement and learning in VET, learning transfer between school and work, and career development and career success over the life span.

Dr Giuseppe Tacconi is Associate Professor for Training and Research Methods at the Department of Human Sciences of the University of Verona and Director of the Centre for Action Research on VET (www.carvet.org). He has focused on issues related to the VET system, having studied in depth and from several points of view the practices and the contexts where VET takes place. His interests are about the epistemology of practice, and the relevance of work experience for the improvement of VET practices and VET Teacher Education.

Dr Marianne Teräs is an Associate Professor at the Department of Education at Stockholm University, Sweden. She has two areas of research interests: professional and vocational education and training and migration and challenges of VET. Her research covers immigration research as well as learning expertise via simulations in the healthcare area.

Dr Özlem Ünlühisarcıklı is an Associate Professor at Boğaziçi University, Faculty of Education, Department of Educational Sciences in Istanbul, Turkey. Her research interests include vocational skill acquisition, apprenticeship and work-based learning, and informal learning in the workplace.

Dr Janis Vossiek holds a Doctor of Social Sciences from the University of Konstanz and currently works as a senior researcher at the University of Osnabrück. A primary focus of his work is the international comparison of vocational training systems and training reforms.

Abstracts

Short abstracts of the participants on the topic of the workshop: Vocational education and training across the lifespan.

Aarkrog, Vibe. In relation to the topic of the research workshop at Vocational Skills week, 2018, there are a number of central themes that could be researched and debated. One theme concerns attracting young people as well as adults to the vocational education and training (VET) system. Concerning the young people, a number of initiatives are currently being implemented. In relation to the adult learners, the attractiveness of VET can be further enhanced through developing systems for making valid and fair assessments of adults' prior learning and through developing adult pedagogy and adult learning environments. Another theme concerns developing opportunities for learning in workplaces and generally in practice. This theme may also include aiming at making practical learning and practical skills more prestigious. Finally, a third theme concerns the interrelation between school-based education and training and workplace-based training. This interrelation is crucial for motivating the students for learning, in particular, theoretical learning and consequently for enhancing the students' learning outcome.

Alessandrini, Giuditta. From my perspective, the most important topics to be discussed regarding the future of VET education are: 1) How to build the competence of "learning to learn". In some international surveys we can find that (i) the average European worker has gone from having a job for life to having more than ten in a career (Source: European Political Strategy Centre, 10 trends: transforming education as we know it, 2017); (ii) young people are more likely than older workers to work in the "gig economy" (more than 40%) (Source: ILO, Global employment trends for youth, 2017). 2) How to prepare young people for "long duration mobility" in the work experience. 3) How VET teachers can stimulate this type of learning process (high-quality didactics). 4) How to develop an evaluation of non-formal learning processes (acquired in the workplace).

Avis, James. The paper engages with a diverse and contradictory literature, employing an analytic stance rooted in policy scholarship. It discusses rhetorical constructions of the Industry 4.0 (4th IR), locating these in understandings of the economy rooted in neo-liberalism which rest upon a capitalist terrain. The 4thIR is an ideological construct which reflects specific material interests, having particular implications for education and training. The 4thIR's association with digitalisation and artificial intelligence (AI) is ambivalent. For some writers this leads to technological unemployment whilst for others, even though there is labour market disruption, there is no employment crisis that cannot be resolved. The strong connection between the 4thIR and labour market requirements are softened by those adopting a qualitative analysis of advanced manufacturing work. These writers suggest the relationship between technology and skill is rather more complex than technological unemployment protagonists suggest. Neo-Marxist discussions of the elimination of labour from paid employment, together with the falling rate of profit, bypasses the former arguments. The paper concludes by arguing that technology and AI are entwined with social relations, being sites of class struggle. How this is played out is an outcome of the balance of power, not only within the social formation but globally. How far the development of the forces of production are compatible with capitalist relations is a moot point, as it is also a site of struggle. The paper draws out the implications for VET over the lifespan and considers what might be progressive educational responses?

Benke, Magdolna. In the future, a number of new challenges — supposed and unknown — will continue to pose new tasks to vocational education and training. These challenges are divided into the following categories: economic, technical-technological, regional, societal-social, pedagogical-psychological. The above groups can form distinct categories through each other, and each of them can call for a number of new research questions. Challenges will not only create new situation for VET decision-makers and VET providers, but also for VET

participants, their families, and those who will employ them. If we look at lifelong VET, I recommend the following long-term questions to be discussed: As the importance of theoretical fundamental professional education increases due to accelerating technological changes, it is a question of how best can VET and lifelong learning help and complement each other? How can the long-term interests related to VET be accepted and supported against the short-term labour market interests? How to build resilience in VET to achieve efficient, successful VET? What technical and pedagogical methods can best help young learners and adults in continuous professional learning? What technical and pedagogical methods can best help learners and adults to build more flexible labour market positions? What type of governance of VET can most effectively help to meet new challenges at each level (micro, meso, macro)? How to support dialogue, partnership and democracy in all level of VET to be able to meet the challenges VET faces across the lifespan?

Biemans, Harm. To enable more students and professionals to reach higher VET levels, it is crucial that boundaries between successive educational levels are reduced. They should be enabled to develop their knowledge, skills, and competencies (required not only for dealing with present and future professional tasks but also for lifelong learning and employability) in seamless learning pathways without artificial barriers between educational levels. In this regard, continuing learning pathways could be implemented in VET systems as curriculum design solutions. Continuing learning pathways can be defined as sequential educational programmes combined into new integrated learning trajectories. For example, in the Netherlands, many experiments have been initiated in the last decade by governmental policy to design and implement continuing learning pathways and, thus, to connect various levels of the VET system. Research on the effects of such experimental learning routes shows that these continuing learning pathways can promote students' transitions to higher VET levels.

Bonoli, Lorenzo. VET set up around 1900 when the choice of profession was a choice for life. Socio-economic and technological conditions then pushed individuals to extend their training through longer study programs or further education. But in recent decades, the challenge has no longer been only to perfect oneself in a profession or branch that remains the same, but to be able to change profession throughout life... but with what consequences in terms of socio-professional identity and integration, and with what consequences for the very notion of profession?

Cechovsky, Nora. From an Austrian perspective initial vocational education and training (IVET) is an important facilitator for social justice. Since the education of a child is still dependent on the educational background of the parents, IVET can provide an important pathway for students from educationally disadvantaged backgrounds and offers a sound vocational education as well as the possibility for further studies. Therefore, IVET has to promote permeability. Consequently, it has to focus next to vocationally relevant skills also on a sound general education. Continuous VET is important to support employability and to react to labour market challenges. All in all, more research is needed on a national level to identify the current challenges and success factors of VET and find ways to further improve its effectiveness and attractiveness. On an international level, research and cooperation is needed to be able to learn from other countries and to support the internationalization of VET.

Deichman-Sørensen, Trine. Vocational education and training across the lifespan — Don't forget the basics! Key issue in European educational policy in recent years was to establish series of novel frameworks in order to promote mobility, flexibility, transparency and permeability institutions and countries across. Even so, VET still makes the one most heterogeneous educational sector in Europe. There is no simple answer to whether this is for the better or worse. As this development proceeds, however, we might need to take a step back. Is, for instance, in recent policy practice too much interests and effort put into establishing an infrastructure of coordination, existing on market level, at the neglect of acknowledging the necessary conditions for instituting a learning society? Research suggest, the importance of provision of

a coherent and systematic initial education is principally demonstrated in its effects later on of providing and enabling collective practices of incremental learning at work rather than any numbers of credentials obtained by individuals on their way. Within current systems these contributions to workplace and employee-driven innovations soon become mute or concealed. Similarly, these systems also tend to fail to encompass basic institutional support to actors operating within emergent occupational domains as, for instance, for youth operating within the up-and-coming and quickly expanding creative sector is the case.

Deitmer, Ludger. One important aspect of vocational education and training (VET) over a lifetime is that professional empowerment is regarded as a progression through different learning areas. The professional learner should be able to combine learning during a seminar or course with practical experience phases to improve work experience and understanding. A gradual improvement of learning in practice and theory should avoid any disruption where only unproductive, less active learning takes place. Therefore, three practical learning areas need a stronger organisational continuity and better integration of theoretical and practical learning phases. These are: work experience and practical learning within the company, training courses provided in the company or at an industrial training centre, and initial or further VET schools. The goal is to avoid major gaps or barriers in successive improvement from initial to further vocational education. This progression could be e.g. an apprenticeship in a recognized and certified occupation. The learning phases alternate with work phases in the workplace.

Dif, M'Hamed. Lifelong learning is generally understood as a continuous building of knowledge, skills and competences throughout the life of individuals. It thus enhances (social and vocational) inclusion, active citizenship, personal and professional development, competitiveness and employability. As VET integrates within the framework of this overarching lifelong learning process, its development over lifespan needs the integration and the promotion of learning path-fluidity and complementarity between and within three types of learning: formal, non-formal and informal learning. This can be achieved basically via: (a)-the development of a complementary procedure for the assessment and qualification/certification-based validation of prior experiential informal and non-formal learning acquired inside and outside working life; (b)- developing/reinforcing the development of work-based learning, especially in its apprenticeship-type alternating training system (c)-improving the attractiveness and the image of VET within the whole educational and training system as a priority learning route leading to “excellence” at all levels.

Dumartin, Eric. Can VET policy just be left to individual initiative? The new French law about training is modifying in depth the existing system of training, based on programs and funds managed by company to convert it into a model based on individual initiative. Is France ensuring the success of what is presented as a training across the lifespan law and called “Law for freedom to choose its professional future”? Are we just entering into a liberalism system or a system with a real pedagogic vision? Apart from breaking an old system with poor results and a lot of money is it enough to say that people can take the lead of their future or can we imagine some improvement based not only on economic ulterior motive but also on a learning country organization?

Evans, Karen, 'Fresh perspectives on vocational learning move beyond pre-occupations with initial VET and young people's transitions to keep in view the system-world, the life-world and the multiple forms of learning that reflexively shape occupational and personal development biographies. These forms extend from pre-VET to post-initial VET to continuing professional development, workplace learning and vocational learning in later adult life. Most research on learning in and for VET has concentrated on young people and initial VET, but increasingly, in ageing societies where the duration of working life is extending, older workers are coming into view. Approaches to vocational learning that embrace a holistic lifelong learning perspective and address the pertinence of factors such as ageing, ethnicity, gender and disability in life

course development have a greater potential to impact on longer term economic and social participation.

Gendron, Benedicte, Vocational education and training VET try discipline covers the lifespan, but (1) on the national level VET research is strongly related to the present implemented national system which generates main areas of research, peripheral regions and lacks. E.g. in countries with an established apprenticeship for the youth, elderly persons are less in focus, and vice versa. The constitution of the national VET systems creates boundaries of research interests and limits the research focus. This is why a European and comparative perspective is essential - on the European level these boundaries, peripheral regions and lacks are not existing. (2) A second line of interest or distinction can be seen between life and work. The construct "work-life-balance" is everywhere present, nevertheless VET research focus just on transitions within and not across, e.g. general school to vocational school, school-to-apprenticeship or school-to-work. The private time and privacy are mostly omitted. This might be also the reason which intersectional approaches are rare. (3) The topic permeability between vocational and academic sector is a perceived challenge in several countries. The intergenerational permeability is on the contrary a widely unperceived challenge which surprises within the context of the demographic change in especially industrialised countries.

Jørgensen, Christian Helms. Vocational education and training across the lifespan — reflections from the Nordic countries. How can initial VET prepare for lifelong learning? Dual systems (apprenticeships) are very effective at providing direct access to employment for the students but tend to reduce long-term employability and divert the students from higher education — and thus to limit the opportunities for life-long learning. The Nordic VET systems offer interesting examples of how this and other trade-offs for VET can be managed. For example, by offering adults extensive opportunities for 'second chances' in free, public adult education with state grants. Norway, Sweden and Denmark offer hybrid apprenticeship programmes that provide both a journeyman's certificate and eligibility for higher education. In Denmark, a training levy contributes to sustain a strong CVET system, which offers skilled workers good opportunities for further training and continuous upgrading of skills. Adults, who never completed upper secondary education, are in the Norwegian apprenticeship system offered a second chance to gain a certificate ('praksisbrev') based on validation of their informal work-based learning.

Kersh, Natasha. Vocational education and training across the lifespan as a means to integrate individuals into the labour market and improve their life chances, has become one of most integral configurations of LLL. It has been increasingly recognized as a core component of national and international strategies for LLL (Evans 2009; Aspin et al. 2012; Malloch et al. 2011), which aim to bring about higher participation and inclusion of young people and adults, including those who are considered to be vulnerable or disadvantaged. Over the last decade, the global recognition of LLL and learning throughout the lifespan has brought attention to the significance of the changing nature, role and various configurations of eco-systems, including a range of learning spaces, networks and contexts. The opening question proposed for the workshop is to consider how the concepts of eco-systems can be used to better both understand individual learning paths and the potential of different types of co-operations within VET and Lifelong Learning.

Laczik, Andrea. Developing employability skills through participating in skills competitions in the UK. In general, there is limited literature on how skills competitions may contribute to young people's skills development and how they impact on young people more general. Using an on-line survey, this piece of research aimed to identify how skills competitions support young people's skills development, how (if) their skills competitions' experiences are used to secure employment and/or progression in a job and what (if) may be the other benefits of taking part in competitions. Using semi-structured interviews, it aimed at better understanding some personal experiences with skills competitions at different levels. The research aimed to capture

mainly the views and experiences of those young people who have not participated in international competitions. This pilot research was conducted early 2018. The findings suggest that young people's expectations of skills competitions were overwhelmingly met. They improved technical skills, were able to demonstrate their existing skills and developed a stronger CV. Young people developed a range of transferable skills, especially problem solving, confidence building, resilience, time management and working under pressure.

Lasonen, Johanna. *Deskilling Educated Immigrants' Career Capital*. The career trajectories of educated immigrants show divergent pathways which is not necessarily beneficial for their career development after leaving home countries. One reason seems to be global mobility, as host countries discount their competencies and skills (Lasonen, 2018). Career capital refers to knowing-how, knowing-whom and knowing-why (Defillippi & Arthur, 1994). The Kaleidoscope Career Model (KCM) by Mainiero and Sullivan (2005) reflects career realities of workers in global contexts. The KCM looks how persons change the pattern of their careers by rotating the varied aspects and periods in their lives to adjust. Three career parameters of the KCM are authenticity (linked to notions of identity and being true to oneself), balance (of work and non-work interest) and challenge (need for stimulating work and career advancement). The purpose of the study was to examine highly education female immigrants' career trajectories and to what extent their competence and skills are accredited. Some 45 immigrant women were depth-interviewed. The interviews were analysed using thematic analyses method. The results showed that highly education immigrant women were partly denied enjoying authenticity and challenge parameters. Instead, they were imposed to non-work interests (balance). Nevertheless, the immigrant women thought positively that migration has provided many benefits to their children.

Lassnigg, Lorenz. *Challenges for the governance of learning across the lifespan — some lessons from the Austrian lifelong learning strategy LLL:2020*. To establish structures promoting lifelong learning for all, politics is asked to provide seamless opportunities for the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and competences with demanding content and coordinated accessibility for learning. VET is competing with general and higher education in initial education and asked to provide substantially expanded provisions of continuous and adult learning. A challenge for the governance of lifelong learning is how to bridge the segmented structures of general, vocational, and higher education, with the alternative approaches of extending education and training markets vs. the strengthening of public institutions. Austria has tried since the 2000s to solve these governance challenges by a comprehensive political lifelong learning strategy (LLL:2020). The analysis of the development and implementation of this strategy shows some challenges that can be taken as an input for a generalized European discussion: How to productively and sustainably involve the various, partly competing, actors? How to mobilise the necessary resources for learning? How to bridge the gaps between vocational and general, and between initial and continuing education? How to effectively apply the various governance instruments (indicators, corporatist negotiations, financial incentives, regulations, etc.)?

Li, Junmin. In contrast to general lifelong learning, the vocational education and training (VET) is always related to the labour market. The trends and needs on the labour market influence the individual's VET decisions across the lifespan and consequently about the demand and supply for a lifelong VET. For the design and promotion of political relevant VET, the comparison and the exchange between different countries within and (outside) of the EU is important in order to capture global developments and to implement them into VET opportunities at the individual level. One key for this transformation is the development of research methods of international comparison and exchange between different VET systems within (and outside) the EU, the discussion about a regional-specific adaption of these findings, in particular, the interpretation and implementation of these findings through stakeholders at the institutional level (e.g. vocational school).

Loogma, Krista. *Narrative understanding of life careers of vocational teachers*. The paper considers the ways how people have become vocational teachers and what factors determine

vocational teachers' career paths. And from another hand, the rapid changes in economy and society, such as all-encompassing digitalization, the cultural changes leading to diversification of the students' body will transform the structural conditions of vocational teachers' work, posing many (new) challenges for them. The paper is based on the concept of career. While individuals' life career is influenced by context factors, as well as by subjective factors like interests, motives, other personal traits (Watson, 1980) and agency. The subjective career, however, refers to the identity, which develops throughout life in interaction with the others (Watson, 1980). Individuals' ability to change and adjust the career path and work identity in circumstances of with changing structural conditions is treated as a high cultural achievement of an individual (Habermas 1976). The empirical case base on sample of vocational teachers in Estonia. The results make visible the patterns, how and why vocational teachers have chosen this career and what kind of choices they made in times, when their opportunity set has radically changed.

Markowitsch, Jörg. Lifelong learning (across lifespan) and lifewide learning (across contexts) have certainly become the most convincing educational ideas of the second half of the past century and constitute today's education paradigm. On the one hand, we must remind ourselves that many of the concepts currently used were quite well elaborated already decades ago. The COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN ECONOMIC COMMUNITY emphasised already in 1963 that VET has 'to promote basic and advanced vocational training and, where appropriate, retraining, suitable for the various stages of working life'. On the other hand, little of these and subsequent ideas (e.g. Faure Report, 1972) have materialised and there seems to be no escape from the Matthew-effect as regards further training. There are a very few countries in Europe which seem to actively embrace a Lifelong learning approach to VET. The questions I would be interested to discuss are: How come that concepts which were quite elaborated in the 1960ies and 1970ies are less advanced today? How can we effectively counteract the Matthew-effect in education and training? How appropriate is an education model based on phases of life in today's world?

Moso-Diez Mónica. New challenges in vocational education and training across lifespan involves connecting VET with innovation. In the knowledge society learning processes are fed back into innovation processes, forming part of the same system where the production, the adaptation, the transfer and the socialization of new knowledge take place. The innovation system is characterized by an intensive use of scientific and technical knowledge, to which VET across the lifespan should be integrated. New challenges in VET across the lifespan imply public policies for research, development and innovation on VET. The development of VET across the lifespan requires a systemic vision of innovation, overarching objectives and effective and efficient mechanisms to integrate the different existing keys (knowledge, innovation, growth, competitiveness, sustainability, etc.), policy domains (education, employment, science and technology, economy and development, etc.), institutional layers (European, national, regional, local) and actions (plans and programmes). The promotion of public policies for research, development and innovation in VET can foster a multiplier effect of lifelong learning itself. Analytical and prescriptive research on new ways of making public policies for research and innovation in VET can be not only a source of useful knowledge, but also a lever for transformation.

Nägele, Christof. Vocational education and training (VET) is about the integration of education, training and work in the work process, based on work tasks. Lifelong-learning describes the principle that any individual needs to update its knowledge, skills and abilities continuously. VET acknowledges, that the task and work processes define not only what and how something needs to be done and learned, but that work defines the identity of an individual and their meaningful careers across the lifespan. VET is at risk to become too much encapsulated in specific occupations and a high specialisation of occupations. Transferring the discourse in the lifelong-learning literature to VET points to the necessity that VET needs to pay attention to

develop individual skills and abilities to adapt to changing environments and to focus on initial and continuous VET as individuals develop through an ongoing dispute between the work and the individual.

Nardi, Paolo. VET faces today an “unknown future” (Mulder, 2017); trainers need not only professional skills for a (less and less) permanent job, rather they have to develop personal capabilities (Nussbaum, 2011) to keep themselves employable: a growth mindset is essential both in the job environment (to feel oneself responsible for the own tasks but also for the company as a whole) and in the job market (to search effectively a job and to get it). Beside internationalization, VET can become more effective if work-based learning or reality-based learning approaches are promoted. The “real” environment, beside and beyond professional skills, provides the trainee with effective circumstances to practice and increase soft skills (problem solving, work in team...). These approaches, however, require key actors (namely companies, educators and students themselves) to have strong commitment and high-quality tools, since the definition of learning agreements to the final evaluation of any work-based experience.

Nokelainen, Petri. Vocational education and training across the lifespan: Supporting development of vocational skills through strengthening of positive activating emotions in school-based and workplace learning settings. Emotions are vitally important during the learning processes of people of all ages, as they affect central cognitive components of learning, attention and memory. Research has shown that positive activating emotions (e.g., enjoyment, hope) are positively associated with engagement in learning and learning outcomes, while negative activating emotions (e.g., anger, anxiety) are associated with undermined learning. Learners’ long-term vision for the development of their vocational skills (e.g., “what trade will I choose in the future”) builds on how they set their performance goals in everyday short-term learning episodes during school-based and workplace learning. Emotions are related to learning motivation, which in turn dictates how learners set these short-term goals. This workshop discusses practical ways of creating learning situations that reinforce learners' positive activating emotions and where learners are supported to become active and self-directed learners who are able to reflect upon their long-term and short-term learning goals.

Ó Murchadha, Eoghan. Vocational Education and Training (VET) in an Irish context is an under-utilised and under-appreciated paradigm of education. Although it plays a significant part in delivering skills to a large cohort of the labour force, it is relegated to a role considered subservient to tertiary education. However, while tertiary education produces individuals with knowledge often based upon nothing more than rote learning, VET more readily prepares individuals for immediate employment by providing skill-sets which can be utilised immediately. Moreover, while tertiary education extols the virtue of higher academic learning through post-graduate qualifications, VET engenders a sense of importance regarding the nature of qualifications based upon its ability to provide more meaningful skills. These individuals, therefore, are more likely to return to upskilling programmes throughout their working life than those with tertiary qualifications, even though the subsequent award is regularly placed at a lower level on the National Framework of Qualifications.

Olmos, Patricia. An inclusive and quality education for all is one of the EU goals. VET can develop a crucial role on the achievement of this goal from a lifelong perspective across the lifespan, especially on the transitions from education into work and into adult work, in the current changing social, educational and labour contexts where such transitions have become a difficult process. To explore which areas around VET role where the perspective of inclusion in education and in the labour market can provide better knowledge in order to improve the quality of VET practices and policies is crucial to this end.

Onstenk, Jeroen. The individualised knowledge-based society demands self-direction from its workers and citizens. They have to be able to find their own destination in the labour market, work, and life in general. If VET is to play a role in lifelong learning it has explicitly to prepare for a (changing) vocational field rather than for specific vocations. VET pathways

should be designed and evaluated, not only with regard to direct (pursued and achieved) learning outcomes, but also with regard to enabling richer and more intensive forms of (informal) learning in the future work situation. VET also has to expand from initial training of young people to offering an array of training opportunities leading to qualifications: certification and recognition of prior competence, making courses more flexible, and contributing to training for adult workers. The challenge is to prepare VET students for the unpredictability of careers, innovation. Changes in occupations, the spreading out into different professions, and to promote agency and employability.

Pilz, Matthias. Comparative research -Learning from others in VET. The issue of how, and to what extent, we can learn from experiences made by different vocational training environments and systems across Europe is of high interest to develop the own VET eco-system and to avoid mistakes already made in other countries. Against this backdrop, it is, however, surprising that there is only little research into the feasibility and successes achieved by such knowledge transfers as well as the long-term impacts of mutual learning. My response/comment formulates major statements concerning research desiderata in the field. The most crucial aspects are the missing theories and methods addressing the heterogeneity and unique nature of VET.

Rachwał, Tomasz. In VET, we should pay special attention to developing entrepreneurship as one of the key competences in European educational systems. It is a general competence but should be treated as an important component of professional competence. This is due to the fact that it means not only the ability to set up own businesses, but also creativity, the ability to solve problems and the willingness to self-education and personal development across the lifespan. In the face of dynamic technological changes, knowledge and skills acquired during vocational education quickly become outdated. Therefore, it is necessary to shape the attitudes of person who will be aware of the need for continuous improvement. Economic and technological changes also put pressure on better qualifications of employees, including a creative approach to solving problems at work. Thus, besides contributing to the creation of businesses, entrepreneurship education will make people more entrepreneurial ('intrapreneurial') in their work, ready to face these challenges.

Rami, Justin. FET in Ireland is not only about employability, it also espouses the key concepts of lifelong learning. It is seen both in policy and structural terms as being one of the main pillars essential to the building and maintenance of a highly skilled work force operating within a knowledge society. The term FET (Further Education and Training) is used in Ireland to encompass Further Education, Vocational Education and Vocational Education and Training (VET). FET is often used interchangeably with VET, depending on the perspective. FET embraces education and training that occurs after second-level schooling and mainly in the further and continuing education sector, though FET also occurs in some Higher Education establishments. The most recent legislation, which marked the establishment of the National Further Education & Training Authority known as SOLAS and ETBs (Education & Training Boards) was in 2013 and covered FET but not VET specifically. In reality this covers vocational education and training, which includes the PLC (Post Leaving Certificate), LCVP (Leaving Cert Vocational Programme), LCA (Leaving Cert Applied) awards and qualifications, adult learning, community education, and vocational training, apprenticeships, on-the-job training, CPD (Continuing Professional Development), internships, other training programmes and labour activation schemes. A distinctive feature of FET in Ireland generally is its diversity and breadth of provision and its links with other services such as employment, training, area partnership welfare, youth, school, juvenile liaison, justice and community and voluntary sector interests. Coincidentally, a wide range of government departments, statutory agencies and voluntary and community based organisations provide services in this area, which adds a greater complexity to the educational system as a whole. Irelands Lifelong Learning participation rate (8.9%) still

lags behind the EU average and the F/VET sector has a long way to go to address this significant deficit.

Rintala, Heta. Vocational education and training (VET) targets a heterogeneous group of students in Finland, aiming to foster social inclusion, promote vocational skills and employment and provide abilities and opportunities for lifelong learning and professional development. In order to assure the attractiveness of VET when compared to general and higher education, VET needs to provide knowledge and occupational skills that facilitate entry into the labour market. However, there is also a need for ongoing development through work and working life. Therefore, VET should also enhance more general skills that are necessary to maintaining educational paths open and keeping pace with continuous changes in the labour market and knowledge society. Work-based learning has a lot of potential to support learning throughout the career, but its quality should be further discussed.

Stalder, Barbara E. Vocational education and training, and learning across the lifespan is a means to acquire, maintain and expand the knowledge and skills that are essential for a successful career. Successful careers provide learners with financial security, quality work, and opportunities for learning, development and individual growth. They fulfil individuals' needs to belong, to be autonomous and to feel competent. It is important to offer high quality initial, higher and continuous VET opportunities to learners with diverse backgrounds, in different life situations, and with different career interests and aspirations. Such opportunities empower and enable individuals to create a career that is sustainable and meaningful for themselves and others. In many, countries VET is seen as a choice for those who have no choice, and the focus is on fostering the employability and social integration of disadvantaged learners. While this remains an important asset of VET, the question arises on how to secure attractive, sustainable and meaningful VET careers of a broader group of learners.

Tacconi Giuseppe. Conceptions of work and conceptions of VET. Rethinking the social and cultural meaning of work across the lifespan to rethink curricula and organization in VET. How do work processes need to be re-conceptualize to let emerge the formative dimension of work? What does it mean knowing in practice? How much wisdom and knowledge is embodied in workplaces and working practices? How can VET appreciate this kind of knowledge? How can work experiences improve students' learning in VET? Which contributions can work-experiences give to the development not only of professional competencies but also of citizenship core competencies? How can the improvement of the quality of work enhance the quality of life in a concrete social and economic environment? Focusing on ideas, processes, actors, and context conditions and using a mainly qualitative methodological approach (analysis of work practices; workplace ethnography; analysis of novels and other cultural products about work; analysis of educational practices in VET) the research tends to generate impacts on micro-level (lived experiences; lived meanings), meso-level (VET providers, VET centres, social partners and stakeholders) and macro-level (governance, VET policies).

Teräs, Marianne. Globalized world with increasing flows of people creates new types of challenges across the lifespan. This study examines school transitions and tensions the young students with immigration background face. Theoretical framework comes from cultural-historical activity theory. The participants were students with an immigration background, parents, and employees of a large city in Finland. Data included qualitative questionnaires and interviews. Analysing method was qualitative thematic analysis. Results suggested that the young faced multiple transitions and tensions with friends, family, and cultural background. School transitions were affected by factors such as individual capabilities, services provided by school and society, and family. In order to support the young in transition phases of their life spans, actions are needed on all levels: individual, community and societal level.

Ünlühisarcıklı, Özlem. The skill set acquired for a vocation is not sufficient throughout the life. One needs to constantly adapt to the technological developments and changing work

situations, which requires not only maintaining the skills that are acquired but developing them. Also, the ability to transfer vocational skills into novel situations is important for a successful work life. Vocational education and training across the lifespan would provide for the vocational skills maintaining and upgrading needs throughout the active vocational life of a worker. As such, vocational education and training across the lifespan will be increasingly important.

Vossiek, Janis. The idea of lifelong learning in the field of vocational training has gained major acceptance among politicians and practitioners alike. However, as training across the lifespan is based on the transition between different educational institutions and providers this also implies the need for a better coordination between government departments, employers and institutions representing learners in order to facilitate transitions between learning phases and institutions. Put differently: A seamless system of training across the lifespan necessitates the seamless cooperation between those actors which are responsible for training provision in order to create attractive options for lifelong learning.

Impetus Presentations

Natasha Kersh, Karen Evans: Lifelong learning and VET: towards understanding the influence of societal eco-systems on learning across the lifespan

Dumartin, Eric. Apprenticeship Reform in France

Ó Murchadha, Eoghan: The VET Skills Cycle and the Formation of Construction Management Skills in Ireland

Fernando Marhuenda and Patricia Olmos: The Role of VET on the Inclusion of Marginalized Young People and Adult People from A Lifelong Perspective Across the Lifespan

Kersh, N., & Evans, K. (2019). Lifelong learning and VET: Towards understanding the influence of societal ecosystems on learning across the lifespan. In C. Nägele, M. Gessler, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Vocational education and training across the lifespan. Report on the VETNET research workshop during the third EU Vocational Skills Week in Vienna, 07.11.2018* (pp. 21–27). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2653539>

Lifelong Learning and VET: Towards Understanding the Influence of Societal Eco-Systems on Learning Across the Lifespan

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Abstract

The impetus of this presentation is to facilitate discussion to reflect on a range of complex interdependencies between lifelong learning (LLL) and vocational education and training (VET), specifically considering the role and influence of societal ecosystems on learning across the lifespan. The VET system, as a means to integrate individuals into the labour market and improve their life chances, has become one of most integral configurations of LLL, fostering social inclusion, participation and skills development across a range of social spaces and contexts. The central question posed by this presentation aims to consider how the concept of ecosystems can be used to better understand both individual learning paths and the potential of institutional cooperation in VET. The discussion further considers how educational services could be made more effective in supporting LLL within workplace, educational and societal ecosystems at different levels (i.e. macro, meso and micro levels).

Introduction

Fresh trends in economic and social development have contributed to the changes in perception of learning through life, the skills required by contemporary learning spaces and the ways that adults engage with a range of networks, contexts and spaces. The position and role of the learner, central to these developments, needs to be better understood, taking into account the complex interdependencies and emerging methods of communication between different contexts and environments.

Vocational and work-based learning has long been recognised as a crucial component of national and international strategies for LLL (Evans, 2009; Aspin et al, 2012; Malloch et al, 2011), which aim to bring about inclusion and lifelong learning of adults across their life span. In this respect, the VET system, as a means to integrate individuals into society and the labour market, has been an important element of LLL and inclusion approaches (e.g. Evans and Niemeyer, 2004). Engaging adults through different forms of LLL has been strongly related to addressing their specific needs and requirements to facilitate their participation in social, economic and civic/political life in their relevant contexts and spaces, both underpinned and influenced by relevant ecosystems and ecologies.

The central points of this discussion as well as questions that we pose in this presentation originate from the 2017 European VET Skills LLL meeting, and relates to the concept of ecosystems and the ways that this concept can be used to better understand individual learning

paths and the potential of institutional cooperation in VET, which is relevant to the emerging findings of the ongoing H2020 project EduMAP¹.

How can the concept of ecosystem be understood?

The concept of ecosystem has been employed in different disciplines as a tool to provide a better understanding of a range of interactions and interdependencies in a variety of contexts, spaces and environments, and there is no universal definition of what constitutes an ecosystem. The definition offered by Hodgson and Spours (2018) provides a helpful framework for a better understanding of how individuals navigate different contexts and spaces while engaging in a range of interactions and communication, and how the spaces and contexts interact and connect through institutional and other types of cooperation and networking. Furthermore, they define a social ecosystem as an evolving place-based, comprehensive social formation focused on the connected worlds of working, living and learning. (Hodgson & Spours, 2018). In this interpretation, connecting the worlds of working, living and learning across the lifespan, happens through a range of cooperation among networks and may take place at macro, meso or micro levels, involving communication and collaboration between key actors. The related concept of communicative ecologies helps to better understand the complex methods of communication and networking in the context of learning through life. In the H2020 EduMAP project communicative ecologies are interpreted as complex systems of communication, media and information flows in a community or group of people (EduMap, 2017). A communicative ecologies approach provides a way of thinking about the ways in which information and communication flows between people and through infrastructures and institutions at they learn through the life course.

Macro level

At macro level, the consideration of wider discourses and ecosystems may contribute to a better understanding of the ways in which society can engage with enhancing LLL and developing vocational education for adults. One influential social discourse emphasises the economic justification of LLL, where the value of LLL is in acquiring job-related skills and competences, i.e. skills that would enable individuals to succeed in the job market. The findings from the current H2020 project (EduMap) indicate that the first discourse provides a very powerful context and rationale for the development of lifelong learning and adult education across Europe. Moving adults into work and enabling them to learn skills required by the contemporary labour market has been considered as one of the most significant prerequisites of adult education courses. Evans (2009) further argues that LLL is more than simply about the intrinsic value of learning or developing the skills and competences required by the labour market. Repositioning adult education within LLL requires a shared philosophy of the purposes and benefits of lifelong learning, which relate to the expansion of human capabilities rather than for merely economic development. Such an approach presupposes that learning is rooted in interactions in the social and material environment as well as in the ways in which people connect new experiences to their prior learning (Illeris, 2009, 2011). Therefore, the consideration of the ways through which institutional and wider societal dynamics might enhance LLL and improve adults' life chances requires a deeper understanding from a socio-ecological standpoint.

¹ EduMap (2016-2018) The project is funded under the European Union's Horizon 2020, Research and Innovation programme, Inclusive, Innovative and Reflective Societies under grant agreement No 693388. This paper reflects only the author's views and the European Union is not liable for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

Meso level

Institutional communication and cooperation are central to the developmental processes of LLL. The conclusions from the EduMap project indicate that communicative practices are highly context-dependent. This applies not only to a specific country context or field of adult education, but can also be relevant for considering different LLL-related programmes within one organisation. The diversity of contexts is also important when considering whether communicative practices can be linked to a specific organisation, and often depends on the interplay between professionals from different organisations. Cooperation is valued among VET providers and help them to shape, develop and redevelop educational programmes for adults.

A key issue is how can we make cooperation between VET providers and other sectors and stakeholders (e.g. higher education, policy makers) work better? These issues that need to be addressed more effectively at the meso level, while at the same time being informed by the micro and macro levels. The findings of the EduMap project have indicated that better collaboration within the same organisation, as well as with external institutions, is one of the key dimensions of a successful programme. Communicative ecosystems and networks play a crucial role in this process.

Micro level

Including analysis of individual and collective learning paths is critically important to responding to these questions. For example, if vocational schools are to provide a stronger platform for LLL, it is important to better understand how vocational schools and initiatives for young adults can build self-esteem. This type of problem has to be understood from the bottom up, not through our assumptions about what the problems are but from the points of view of participants – including students, teachers and employers. Including research at the micro-level often problematises policy responses in order to improve them. Not only shared understandings of the participants but also links and learning paths from pre-school to adults and beyond to later life have to be understood if we are serious about transforming vocational education. Understanding the roots of vocational learning from the early years and growing from them is a multi-level research challenge that explores the interrelationships between the micro, meso and macro levels. Communication challenges, linked to limited confidence, skills or awareness, are another indication of the struggles faced by some young people. An overall key finding emerging from the EduMap project is the importance of a match between learner needs, motivations and aspirations with adult education/VET programme content, methods and contexts of delivery. The influence of relevant ecosystems and ecologies needs to be taken into account.

A socio-ecological approach requires the development of more participatory research – communication ecologies operate through networks that build these shared understandings and develop them into interventions. Building shared understandings of the perspectives and capabilities of participants in VET is one of the core elements. Teachers and trainers as social actors play a key mediating role in the openness of institutions to new ideas about VET and vocational learning throughout the life course

Questions for discussion

The following central research question and sub-questions were identified:

How can concepts of ecosystems be used to better understand learning paths and the potential of institutional cooperation in VET, in order to find out how to make educational services more effective in supporting lifelong learning within business, educational and societal ecosystems?

- How can the concept of ecosystems facilitate an understanding of the dynamics at macro level? How are social and economic changes impacting on the conception of VET?
- How can we make cooperation between VET providers and other sectors and stakeholders at meso level (e.g. higher education, policy makers) work better?

- how can we ensure a match between learner needs, motivations and aspirations with adult education/VET programme content, methods and contexts of delivery? How can recognition of skills and competences be expanded to better recognise multiple forms of expertise in action?

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Minutes

The discussion that followed the presentation emphasised a number of significant issues that need to be taken into consideration and further explored when researching aspects of lifelong learning (LLL) and vocational education and training (VET). The following questions were considered:

1. How can the concept of ecosystems facilitate an understanding of these dynamics? How are social and economic changes impacting on the conception of VET?
2. How can we make cooperation between VET providers and other sectors and stakeholders (e.g. higher education, policy-makers) work better?
3. How can we ensure a match between learners' needs, motivations and aspirations with adult education/VET programme content, methods and contexts of delivery?
4. How can recognition of skills and competences be expanded to better recognise multiple forms of expertise in action?

These questions were formulated to facilitate discussion and offered an initial impetus for consideration of the key issues related to the questions above. The discussion that followed drew on these questions as starting points, leading to the development of emerging cross-cutting themes which have indicated overlaps and interconnections between key points highlighted by the questions.

The concept of VET and LLL

Considering the concept of VET and LLL was recognised as an important starting point. The discussion stimulated valuable reflections on the interrelationships between VET and LLL. These two concepts need further exploration in the context of current developments and discourses. As has been noted, identifying some common elements of LLL and VET could contribute to enhancing conceptual clarity and a better understanding of both common and distinguishing features between LLL and VET. VET is an integral part of the LLL discourse, providing opportunities for both acquiring occupationally related skills and facilitating social inclusion, employability and active citizenship.

The discussion has indicated that in today's LLL and VET programmes, there are some important challenges that need to be addressed across all levels (micro, meso and macro):

1. Understanding the nature and purposes of LLL is of crucial significance: e.g. training for lifelong learning (training to learn how to learn) versus training for a job.
2. The challenge highlighted by the discussion is how to facilitate not only learning for employability, inclusion and citizenship, but also developing an environment that would support a 'Joy to learn' concept. This is an important prerequisite that could be one of the contextual factors for the development of a meaningful learning environment.

One of the main concerns raised within the discussion related to the questions of the extent to which different political and social discourses and contexts may affect and shape approaches to LLL and VET. For example, the economic agenda (training for specific jobs rather than training to learn) may hinder the LLL outlook for learners.

Ecosystems and discourses

The discussion has suggested that the ecosystem approach has the potential for helping researchers to better understand different types of interactions in a range of contexts and environments, offering a systematic approach to exploring the nature of interrelations and communications. However, the concept of ecosystems has often been conceptually contested, and there is no universal definition of what constitutes an ecosystem. The challenges associated with the use of this concept in research have been identified, as follows:

1. There is no clear distinction in the literature between related concepts such as communicative ecosystems, networking, ecologies and social discourses. These concepts need to be better defined and the relationships between the concepts need to be explored and understood.
2. Exploring ecosystems in addition to context and localism and the three levels (micro, meso and macro) could contribute to a better conceptual understanding of this notion, as these are in constant flux.
3. Is ‘social/societal ecosystem’ the best term to describe the links between living, working and learning (socio-economic system)? Traditionally this concept has had a strong biological meaning; therefore, applying it to social science research requires careful consideration.
4. Why should the concept of ecosystem be better suited than, for example, community, networks, etc?

Cooperation between VET providers and other sectors and stakeholders

The question of the importance of the development of networks and collaborations between all stakeholders involved in VET and LLL was raised continuously throughout the discussion. The key points relating to the challenge of making the collaboration between VET providers and other key stakeholders meaningful were addressed and considered during the meeting. One important issue was highlighted: that the nature of the collaboration between the providers/key stakeholders is of a bidirectional relation, not just a responsive one. This means that the channels of communication and cooperation represent a system of shared interactions between practitioners, policy-makers and other key stakeholders. Otherwise, there is concern that there is a risk that the trainers’ and teachers’ perspectives will be lost. One important point that was emphasised is that cooperation should also focus on learning at work and informal learning, which includes a reflection about how work and tasks have to be shaped to foster learning. It is of crucial importance to develop collaboration and build up trust between sectors. In respect of cooperation the following points have been noted:

1. The question of cooperation needs to be considered across all levels (micro, meso and macro), developing strategies and approaches to facilitate the interlinks and connections between these levels.
2. Developing common goals is of utmost importance. Careful planning needs to take into account three key actors (VET institutions, companies or labour market, and VET learners).
3. Involving employers would be a challenge, because they do not always look to upscale their employees either vocationally or personally.
4. The major challenge is that cooperation is important, but also difficult. What is the aim of cooperation in VET? Are employers willing to cooperate if the aim is to promote social inclusion?

Supporting learners

Support for learners needs to be an important goal across all three levels (micro, meso and macro). A shared understanding of learners’ needs, motivations and ambitions needs to be taken into account and addressed through cooperative and communicational structures. VET and LLL should address not only equipping learners with vocational and job-related skills, but also offer them opportunities for lifelong learning and personal development, social inclusion, development of social networks and active citizenship.

Placing learners at the centre of the learning process should be considered a priority of LLL approaches. It is of crucial importance to allow for more student/learner participation in the development of the process (e.g. the development of curricula/standards). As noted, ‘*Putting learners in the centre should become a reality and not just lip service.*’

In undertaking future research, taking into account the individual level (micro level) has been highlighted as an important research approach, i.e. research needs to start at the individual level by interviews (e.g. including questions on individual learning biographies) to understand the problems faced by young people and adults. This can be the basis for further investigations at institutional (meso) and societal (macro) levels .

Recognition of learners' prior skills was emphasised as a strategy that contributes to the development of motivation and confidence and, therefore, this strategy should be incorporated into LLL and VET learning discourses. However, vocational guidance should consolidate both the recognition of past experiences and a '*prospective approach*' (looking ahead in terms of development of skills for the future).

Conclusions

The consideration of these cross-cutting themes indicates that LLL and VET often overlap and involve complex processes, which both influence and are being influenced by ecosystems and ecologies. Cooperation between stakeholders is a crucial component of VET, which is being continuously developed and shaped across the three levels (micro, meso and macro). A socio-ecological approach can contribute to better understanding how communicative ecologies operate through networks that build on these shared understandings in relation to the purposes and aims of VET. Building shared understandings of the needs, capabilities and ambitions of participants in VET is one of the core elements. Key stakeholders (such as teachers and trainers) play a key mediating role in the development of this shared understanding while making inter-connections between the three levels (micro, meso and macro).

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Apprenticeship Reform in France

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Introduction

Amazingly the reform of apprenticeship is coming after the first growth of apprenticeship after ten years (7,4% in 2017!), making probably more difficult the analysis of its effects.

Is the reform answering the criticisms and aligning French apprenticeship on the best in class systems and on EU VET objectives?

At the first reading the reform appears like a list 20 different measures without hierarchy, making it hardly decipherable, going from an increase of 30,00 € per month of apprentice payment (first measure) to the enlargement of maximum apprentice age from 25 to 30. Can we find the top 5 “iconic” measures of that list?

1. Any alternating contracts will be funded.
2. The learning funding system will be fully reviewed, using a simple, transparent and secure principle: a youth + a company = a contract = a financing. All contracts will be funded in all sectors regardless of the size of the company.
3. The search for a business by a young person will no longer face the problem of financing the contract.
4. The hiring aids will be unified and focused on the small and very small companies and the lowest qualification levels.
5. The hiring of apprentices can be done throughout the year and will be much less constrained by the school pace.
6. The governance of apprenticeship will be withdrawn to regions for the benefit of professional branches
7. Apprenticeship schools will be funded contract by contract and not globally.

Apprenticeship reform hits

If we look into more details to the reform, we must emphasize the following points:

The basic objective is to increase apprenticeship numbers by an optimization of funds and by aligning diplomas with professional branch’s needs.

As if there is no real reference to it, is it making echo to the EU objective for 2020: “VET systems should be more attractive and accessible to all, providing quality education with high labour market relevance. They must be flexible enough to allow permeability between the different education systems...”?

As an answer, the age limit to sign an apprenticeship contract is pushed from 25 to 30 and apprentices will have the possibility to enter into their training all along the year, out of school periods.

Contract duration can be adapted in regards of trainee existing competences. The minimum duration of an apprenticeship contract is 6 months instead of 1 year. Apprenticeship contract

duration can also be adapted following professional branch's needs (under collective agreement conditions) with a minimum of 25 % of time spent at school.

Apprentices will be entitled to work up to 35 or 40 hours a week under conditions.

Regarding financial assistance for apprentices:

The minimum wage is increased by 30 € net per month and for the eldest the salary will come closer from minimum wage. An additional aid to get driving license will be given (500 €) and a part of the training can be followed abroad (Erasmus).

The opening of schools (CFA) is made easier:

The regions will not decide any more of the opening of training centers (CFA). The administrative authorization system is deleted. A training company can become a CFA just after declaration and must have a quality certification process. Apprenticeship schools will be funded contract by contract by France Compétences and not globally by their regions.

Aids for companies are also modified:

A unique aid for companies with less than 250 employees will be given by the government (probably 3000 € per year and per contract).

Tax for companies are following the same objective of simplification:

The training contribution is now unique but divided into 2 parts: contribution for training and apprenticeship tax. This global contribution will be recovered by the tax collector administration. The apprenticeship tax remains unchanged at 0,68% of gross salary, 87% of that amount being poured to France Compétences, and 13% left to companies' initiative (2 parts instead of 3 previously).

France Compétences, a new agency under Work Minister control will have a central role for funds distribution. The governance of the system that was very complex is now much more readable.

Figure 1 Governance before reform

Figure 2 Governance after reform

Is the Apprenticeship reform answering both French and EU objectives?

The French reform doesn't make any reference to European Union objectives but amazingly we can't help recognizing some nearness.

We can summarize the reproaches made to the previous system: too complex tax and subsidies, lack of flexibility of the system (mainly the rhythm of courses/ companies work organization), inadequate content of courses in regard of company's needs, huge complexity and inefficiency of apprenticeship governance, low attractiveness for students. Last but not least, the negative influence of National Education was pointed out.

The first answer is matching France and EU VET attractiveness objectives "making initial VET an attractive learning option and fostering the excellence, quality and relevance of VET to the labour market".

Many iconic measures are answering this objective:

- "1 employer + 1 apprentice = 1 funded contract" is creating a mandatory link between labour market and apprenticeship. It clearly appears that this principle is excluding VET without a link to labour market;
- orientation is not left at the National Education but at the regions as they know manpower needs in their areas. Many blames were weighing on the lack of consideration of NE regarding apprenticeship, so we can expect some improvement in VET attractiveness;
- professional branches leadership on CFA creation. This is probably the key measure of the reform. Until now the collected taxes went to the regions that redistributed it to their schools. The new system is much simpler: the schools are paid for each apprenticeship contract. This is the end of an obscure system made of political subsidies. Until now the regions could maintain the activity of their local schools for political considerations, with the new system the only survivors will be the schools answering real manpower needs as if an envelope of 250 M€ will be maintained to balance some critical cases in the regions. Professional branches become the pivot point of professional world in apprenticeship system. But amazingly, becoming a school delivering VET is now opened to all training companies. The positive contribution of these new comers will be innovative learning and challenging some existing positions.

- Designing of VET diplomas is now a prerogative of professional branches to the detriment of NE.

The employability of graduates is the marker of the reform. From a student perspective it is reinforcing the attractiveness of apprenticeship that becomes the way to a job with a very limited risk of unemployment.

The second answer aligned with EU objectives is about flexibility and simplifying access to training and qualifications.

Three measures can be pulled out to illustrate the effort to improve flexibility:

- the possibility to enter into apprenticeship at any time during the year, the rigidity of scholar agenda being one of the main brakes to company's collaboration.
- some decrees will be published to enlarge access conditions to apprenticeship for unemployed and people living with minimum social wage in a « difficult area ». Without delay an inter-ministerial delegate has been nominated to support apprenticeship in popular areas. One of his missions will be to align local competences with companies needs via apprenticeship.
- for young with a lack of basic competences (writing, reading...) a preparation course will be created upstream the apprenticeship courses. Moreover, as aids are now focused on lowest qualifications we can hope that apprenticeship will return to its initial vocation instead of growing on the highest levels.

The simplification of incentive and tax systems but also of registration process are reinforcing the strategy of facilitating access to VET.

The international mobility in VET, an EU objective, is also encouraged by the new law with the introduction of a pan European measure allowing to follow a part of the training abroad.

The quality of training of CFA, again an EU objective, will be piloted via a unique system of control and certification under France Compétences responsibility. National Education is also losing here a part of its autonomy.

Were the European Union objectives for VET a consistent guideline for France?

If we look wording and objectives, we can be struck by their convergence as if it was not publicly expressed.

The French reform is offering an interesting declension with concrete answers. On the other side it would be amazing to see if those solutions could be applicable in European countries facing the same challenges...

The main logic of the reform is to give the leadership to professional branches and create a competition environment to ensure employment opportunities after VET.

Still in the competition mind, it will be very interesting to see how IVET and CVET² will work together and/or compete. With 665 000 IVET students in 1500 schools on one side (National Education) and 430 000 CVET apprentices in 950 CFA on the other side (Professional branches) we can hope the new law will be challenging and improve their offer.

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Minutes

The debate about the French reform of apprenticeship has raised a major question, « is the objective (increasing apprenticeship number) justifying the methods » ? In French we say « the end justifies the means » and behind this question the second question could be a deeper one, **what should we save from apprenticeship to maintain its vocational spirit.**

Before trying to answer this debate two things from the debate must be specified:

- The apprenticeship reform we discuss here is focused on CVET and doesn't include National Education path as these paths are not under an employment contract condition. It doesn't include either the past professionalization period system and professionalization contract (as if they have been modified by the reform). The difference between National Education new strategy regarding professionalization and Professional branches strategy regarding apprenticeship will be an exciting subject of study.
- **The apprenticeship reform is answering most of the drawback of past French system**, most of the Stockholm objectives... and some of the difficulties raised by some participants in their country... ! If we have a quick examination of past/actual situation this should be the first conclusion.

But **despite a reform that could look like a major improvement** some measures seem to have particularly raised some worries from the participants, opening a potential quarrel between supporters of a pure line and defenders of a pragmatic approach.

If we try to pick up the major worries and bring them together under a single call, "quality", they are:

- Minimizing « at school » time
- Reducing length of VET period at a minimum of 6 months
- Opening to private training companies and companies the possibility of creating VET schools (CFA)
-

And going further, this reform is opening a more global thinking about the governance of an apprenticeship system and the role of National Education versus branches and companies.

1. "Quantity versus Quality".

Let's try to discuss the first visible drawback of the reform, we could say "Quantity versus Quality".

By lowering the minimum duration of contract and time spend at school there is probably a positive effect on attractiveness versus transmission of knowledge. This amendment was targeting the high abandon rate (25%). We can surely argue we are choosing numbers and favorite natural tendency of students against school, an easy solution, but we must also know that the government is fighting against "time for time" practice that says that the longer the course, the more efficient the learning. Of course schools like this practice also synonym of "the longer the course, the more money we have"... This approach, cost effectiveness, is now fought by the

government under the pedagogic revolution banner, and the new definition of the training action, we must shorten the learning path if we can arrive to the same progression objective.

Pedagogy is coming upstream and there is probably a large scope of experimentation to make that idea a reality. It should be interesting to investigate more about that topic (suggestion of a workshop participant) but we don't have yet a consistent material.

Enlarging the maximum age to enter into apprenticeship to 30 years can't really be attached to a pedagogic theory. The results of 2018 similar experimentation, weighing 50% of apprenticeship increase in numbers is probably the only reason.

The measures are in fact making closer apprenticeship and Professional VET, shorter, flexible, cheaper...

The discussion came also about the possibility offered to training companies and companies themselves to open their own CFA (apprenticeship school). Isn't that going too far into liberalism option, don't we have the risk to lose the knowledge and experience build by the past system in collaboration with National Education...?

Since Vienna research meeting, an extraordinary and unexpected precision about the vision of the French government came from an interview of the Director of the cabinet of the work Minister, Antoine Foucher. The (real) title was "what would I do with the apprenticeship law if I was a HR Director?". Not only this interview is confirming some participants concerns but it is going further in the liberal possibilities of the law. The best thing to do is to deliver a complete translation of the interview (AEF interview, DÉPÊCHE N°596649) .

"The law will facilitate the establishment of companies CFA "with legal certainty to open and create very simply a CFA for those who have an internal university or even a privileged link with a training organization. Open your CFA now and then you have 18 months to obtain CFA certification, "says Antoine Foucher, pointing out that the law will also help to secure the initiative economically.

"This new framework will make it possible to invest the 13% of the learning tax dedicated to the discharge expenses in the creation of an internal CFA, then it will be possible to use part of the remaining 87% to invest in this structure. An opportunity that should interest the directions of financial affairs of companies, "says Antoine Foucher, making the link with the easing that will allow this new framework.". By internalizing, companies will be able to recruit and train apprentices according to the needs of their 'business model', but also send their apprentices to their subcontractors as in the German model," he continues, adding that this model corresponds rather to big companies.

Another opportunity that will be offered by the reform: establish a privileged partnership with one or more CFA to encourage them to meet the specific needs of the company. "The goal will be for the partner to integrate the needs of the company into their offer, for example by asking them to be able to take in apprentices all year round. It is not on the price but on the quality of the service that it will be necessary to "challenge" the CFA, for example on the duration of the courses which can be too long. If the company does not obtain satisfaction it will be able to see another CFA ", continues Antoine Foucher."

"The third model is the one that will evolve the least, it is to play the competition by using several CFA, to the extent that everyone can adapt in real time to the needs of the company. The first two models are interesting and develop the competitiveness between companies, by increasing the attractiveness of those who invest in these opportunities. The third can work but it is not desirable to limit themselves to compete with the CFA, because it can induce to change all the years of CFA ", Antoine Foucher analysis.

This interview is really designing the way the reform has been imagined: from companies needs to CFA offers, in a very competitive environment where CFA are challenged every year ("it is not a question of price" but it should become if it is just left to companies decision...), and where the apprenticeship tax can be 100% recycled internally by the company! Usually companies have to pay experts to understand how to "optimize" a new law, the solution is given

that time directly by the government! Not only a saving, a sign made to (big) companies, this reform is for you...

A workshop participant has very well summarize the risks linked to this change of paradigm: “ In general, companies and branches think about their own interests rather than creating a comprehensive VET system, so you couldn’t change it so radically without NE strategy (focused on whole system) and control”.

But can’t we imagine a consistent and systemic apprenticeship system without NE control? We must not forget past reproaches made to NE and its lack of understanding of companies ‘needs. The concern could be that we’ve moved from black to white (or white to black) – “a too quick shift from school-based to company-based” - when the governance solution could be grey... A workshop participant is proposing a solution: “the system appears more as an internship program than an apprenticeship program, because the **collective regulation and standardization is missing**”.

Another crucial information given by Antoine Foucher is about quality. As we see efficiency is put ahead, the system will have to make the efforts in terms of certification later.

So, for sure, we can be worried about the quality of apprenticeship training in France. A workshop participant says that “**social responsibility perspective is needed**” to guaranty the **quality of the training**. This is also a good point and there is probably something to include around that notion in the coming decrees for the quality of apprenticeship.

The draft decree for quality lays down the procedures for organizing the control for diplomas issued. Training leading to a professional title is not concerned.

The pedagogical control of apprenticeship training should focus on "the implementation of the training with regard to the reference system of the diploma concerned". It will be carried out "on parts and places of training of apprentices" (companies and CFA).

Each certifying ministry will have to set up a pedagogical control mission for the diplomas which concern it and determine their organization and their mode of operation. The control will be exercised jointly by the following persons:

- inspectors from the certifying ministries (or public officials authorized according to the rules of the ministries concerned);
- the experts designated by the professional branches.
- the experts appointed by the consular chambers. They will be designated "at the request of the regional prefect".

The text specifies that this activity of pedagogical control is "incompatible with a function or a mandate" in a CFA.

These missions will have to transmit each year "a provisional plan of the controls and a report of activity to the prefect of region". The latter will prepare an annual summary report of activities and recommendations. It will be presented to the Regional Committee for Employment, Training and Vocational Guidance.

It is not sure that this project, organizing control by some stakeholders will reassure the advocates of quality...

2. National Education loss of influence

We didn’t spend a lot of time on the articulation of orientation between National Education and entrance in apprenticeship. But it is key for the system.

Amazingly, while NE is losing its influence, it is showing a new dynamism about professionalization. At the very moment when it loses his influence he has never been so successful! To be a bit provocative we could say that branches and companies should inspire of the new collaborative system imagined by NE to boost IVET...

Despite that we must recall two numbers that could justify the preference given to apprenticeship: insertion rate for apprentices (7 months after the end of training) is 67% for

apprenticeship schools and only 48% for professional schools (NE). An expert (Daniel Vatant) is explaining the difference: employers are choosing their apprentices while NE is not choosing its students...! And these figures do not reflect the 25% abandon rate in the apprenticeship system.

In the law, the absolute priority for apprenticeship also translates, unsurprisingly, into a reduction in the financial resources that can be perceived by vocational schools under the apprenticeship tax. The fraction of this tax that can be allocated by employers to vocational training outside apprenticeship is suddenly reduced from 23% to 13%, (a potential loss of resources of the order of 300 M €).

It should also be remembered that the governance of apprenticeship will no longer be the responsibility of the Regions but that of the professional branches. It is of course legitimate, and even necessary, for branches to be actors of learning. But they are not a public service: is learning privatized?

Conclusion

The searchers and participants of the workshop are “pure” defenders of the concepts of VET while in the same time the French Government has made efficiency a priority.

We can just notice that these two worlds are in a way ignoring themselves... One of the participant question was “where does come from or get inspired this reform...?”. Probably not from VET searchers will be my answer, but isn't that a good revelator of our margin of progress in terms of cooperation? Some searchers call to mind that VET liberalization in Poland was a fail and that rebuilding the VET system was not easy after that attempt. From these alerts we can suggest that the first months of the reform should be particularly followed in order to put in place corrective actions if necessary.

I have tried during the workshop to underline the fact that the apprenticeship reform was bringing answers to most past drawbacks, while not minimizing the risks.

Despite that, the reform was not positively received by our group of searchers and experts for the reasons mentioned above.

We can probably regret the lack of exchanges between deciders and the community of specialists of apprenticeship.

But maybe it is not too late to establish a new cooperation model, with a governance including VET specialists.

Anyway, the results of the reform will have to be analyzed with a lot of attention.

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The VET Skills Cycle and the Formation of Construction Management Skills in Ireland

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Introduction

Human capital within the construction industry in Ireland is made up of a myriad of individuals who each perform a relatively siloed function within the operation and management of construction projects. For instance, most of these individuals are tertiary educated academics (engineers, architects etc.) who do not operate to any great extent outside of the parameters of their own specific knowledge base.

There is, however, one individual who performs the function of ‘lynchpin’ in the entire project management process – the construction manager. This person, often called a ‘foreman’, ‘site agent’ or ‘project manager’ is invariably someone who has progressed through various levels of VET. Without this person’s vocational knowledge and understanding of the operation of all aspects of the construction process, projects would not be achievable within programme or budget.

And yet, the development of this individual almost exclusively begins with the earliest level of engagement in VET – apprenticeship. These individuals, through the course of their working lives, attain the position of construction managers where their vocational experience is vital to the operation of the project team. Therefore, threats to skills cycles impede not only the provision of apprentices and tradespeople but also that of future management supply.

Background

Within any economy the construction industry is a vital sector of industry as it delivers the potential for economic growth via the provision of building and infrastructural needs which the rest of the economy and society requires in order to thrive. In Ireland, the importance of the construction sector cannot be over-stated. It has long been a major provider of employment and by virtue of such has consequently been a “key generator of wealth” for the economy (Forfás, 2013). Therefore, a symbiotic relationship has developed between Ireland’s construction industry and macro economy. This relationship, however, has not always been beneficial to both sides as was seen in the catastrophic collapse of the Irish economy in the mid 2000’s.

A consequence of the above economic downturn was the severe contraction of the construction industry. This led to the inevitable increase in unemployment of construction operatives, tradespeople and professionals. One often over-looked casualty of this was the apprenticeship cohort. In Ireland, traditional apprenticeships have been used as the educational paradigm of construction industry related trades, i.e. the construction labour force. Therefore, when construction employment declined, there was an associated reduction in apprenticeship employment also.

This, however, is not surprising, as Lassnigg (2017) postulates that there is a direct relationship between the demand for apprentices and that of labour generally. Moreover, the

supposition is made that this relationship is cyclically tied to economic performance and therefore exacerbated by periods of economic duress.

Apprentice employment

At peak, before the impact of the aforementioned recession, apprentice employment in Ireland was in excess of 30,000 individuals (2005, n=30,319). With the impact of the economic downturn, this figure declined to just over 7,000 apprentices at its lowest point (2013, n=7,125). This represents a reduction of 76 percent of the total apprenticeship population. Even more stark is the statistic regarding new apprenticeship registrations. Before the recession, new apprentice recruitment was steady, recording in excess of 8,000 individuals annually (2006 peak, n=8,306). However, as with the figures above for apprentice employment, the economic downturn reduced this figure drastically. A reduction of 86 percent from peak to trough occurred in just four years (2010, n=1204).

The significance of this statistic is often overlooked by policy makers. Apprenticeship is not simply a method by which to provide cheap labour in the form of semi-skilled operatives (Franz & Zimmermann, 2002). On the contrary, apprentices are a component of direct construction employment. They are productive in their own right and given the “market driven” nature of this educational paradigm, apprentices produce a benefit for their employers by virtue of their productivity (Mühlemann, Wolter & Wüest, 2009).

Moreover, apprentices provide the basis of a skills-cycle within the construction labour market. Through their training and they supply industry with a mechanism by which to consistently replenish skills availability. Without this cycle the threat of a skills gap is pervasive. The importance of this issue has been noted by the Irish national training authority SOLAS. They have stated that “the availability of qualified tradespersons may become an issue as the recovery in the labour market continues” (Skills & Labour Market Research Unit, 2015).

Implications to management

In addition to the threat of a skills gap, there exists another potential deficit within the labour force, brought about by a lack of apprentices, i.e. the supply of appropriately skilled construction managers.

Even more so than a method of replenishing the skills cycle, apprentices are a foundation occupation of VET. Apprenticeship provides an initial stage of education for individuals who have the capacity to develop and transfer their skills to alternative professions (Mohrenweiser & Backes-Gellner, 2010). Apprentices are a link in the chain of the hierarchical labour force structure within the construction industry (O’Connor & Harvey, 2001). By virtue of their VET route through education and their experiential development, apprentices have the capacity to develop over time from tradespeople to managers (Skills & Labour Market Research Unit, 2008).

Within the traditional construction project management team, all members other than the construction manager traditionally follow tertiary educational routes. Though all vital members of the project team, those such as the architect, engineer and surveyor have all pursued non-VET, academic paths to employment. This siloed manner of learning and delivery of function does nothing to endorse these individuals as suitably effective construction managers.

The task of co-ordination of the construction project and the translation of management decisions into instructions to the labour force is a precarious one as project budgets and programmes are directly affected by the ability of the workforce to deliver value for money. The duty of maintaining time, cost and quality of a project is that of the construction manager; whose role is often under appreciated.

This individual requires a broad knowledge and skillset from which to draw upon, developed preferably through experience. Therefore, the ideal candidate for this role is frequently a person who has followed a route of experiential learning, often beginning with an apprenticeship as explained by Mohrenweiser and Backes-Gellner (2010).

Future labour supply

The skills supply situation outlined above should not be under-estimated. As stated, the obvious negative implication for the Irish construction industry brought about by a decline in apprenticeships is that of a skills deficit. However, lessons may be learned from other countries where this issue has been witnessed.

In the UK, a report published by The Work Foundation (2010), described how skills shortages prevail more than a generation after recommendations were made to invest in labour market skills. This is disturbing given the fact that a recent study of construction firms in Ireland reported that 86 percent of employers already feel that a skills gap is present within the Irish construction industry. More worrying still is that 71 percent of these respondents do not currently employ apprentices thereby compounding the problem of future skills availability (Ó Murchadha & Murphy, 2018).

Regrettably, the information above would seem to indicate that Ireland is facing a potential skills crisis. It is therefore vital that all stakeholders to apprenticeship in Ireland collaborate and act now to ameliorate the potential future skills catastrophe.

Regarding the theme of vocational education and training across the lifespan, it is obvious that apprenticeship potentially delivers a springboard from which to develop lifelong learning. However, the issue is academic if the opportunities for initial skills development do not exist.

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Minutes

A presentation of the above paper was made by the author to a workshop of VETNET researchers. The session was moderated by Prof. Michael Gessler. Prof. Gessler introduced the presentation by summarizing the Irish economic context in relation to VET training and, apprenticeship. He further reminded those present of the VETNET meeting in Dublin in 2016 where the impact of recession upon VET training had been discussed. This introduction set the background for the presentation and paper.

Upon completion of the presentation, the assembled participants were instructed to discuss the details and findings presented and to consider the questions posed at the end by the presenter. These questions were as follows:

Q1: Can macro/exo level mechanisms be used to prevent skills deficits occurring?

Q2: How can employer engagement in apprenticeship be maximized?

Q3: Should management level occupations be filled via tertiary level education only, to avoid a skills deficit?

Feedback from the floor was collected via Mentimeter which was overseen and collated by Prof. Barbara Stalder. The author and presenter then answered those questions which were particularly relevant and pertinent to the discussion at hand in the workshop.

Attending researchers at the workshop made relevant statements in relation to several factors regarding the issues raised in the presentation. Notable points included the following:

- IVET was highlighted as a mechanism to offset future skills deficits through early adoption of VET skills.
- The need for state subsidization of employers (particularly micro-firms) was noted as a measure to improve employer engagement in training thereby limiting the potential for deficits in skills availabilities.
- Additionally, the question arose as to why/how employers would/could engage in apprenticeship training.

These issues are considered in the concluding remark below

Conclusions

The traditional apprenticeship system in Ireland, the Standards Based Apprenticeship is connected for the most part either directly or indirectly with the construction industry. Therefore, the current range of apprenticeships in Ireland differs greatly than most European states in that it is not extensive but rather limited in scope. However, this 'limitation' has resulted in the evolution of apprenticeship in Ireland as a specialized paradigm for the delivery of key skills for industry. Through this specialization the construction manager has emerged as a highly competent individual based upon his/her vocational training and work-based learning. This is not a scenario which is easily replicated in a non-VET paradigm of learning. Due to the nature of the experiential learning and tacit skills acquisition of tradespeople, the cycle of skills through apprentice-tradesperson-manager is a form of CVET.

An analogous issue to that of a limited range of apprenticeship, is Ireland's position in terms of IVET. Since Ireland has a standardized post-primary educational route, IVET at upper secondary level is not an available option to commence preparatory VET skills formation. Apprenticeship is the most prevalent form of VET in Ireland, and in its current guise is a post-secondary form of education. The option, therefore, to offset future skills gaps by commencing skills formation at secondary level is not currently possible within Irish VET.

As outlined in the presentation and paper, the impact of the lack of skills upon the pillars of commerce (*time, cost & quality*) is potentially detrimental to the industry. Skills deficits negatively affect the capacity to deliver upon time and quality thereby increasing the cost factor of projects. This is an obvious detraction to any business model but is particularly egregious to the construction industry. This is because the construction industry in Ireland not only relies earnestly upon its ability to respond to the needs of society but more importantly to the demands of foreign direct investment. If the industry is unable to deliver value for money, then investors

will simply go elsewhere. Value for money is symbiotically linked to the availability of requisite skills.

Given the importance of experientially developed construction management skills in achieving value for money and the critical role of the VET skills cycle in the formation of these skills, it is vital that the skills agenda be addressed at the highest level. Although Ireland has a small apprenticeship training sector, it has nonetheless developed very robust social partnerships in the delivery of VET skills. However, given the socio-ecological nature of the apprenticeship structure, and the fact that macro-level policy mandates the delivery of standards in Ireland, State level intervention is required to effect change.

The onerous nature of legislative obligations upon employers has caused a reluctance amongst firms to invest in VET. This is understandable given that most firms in the Irish construction industry employ ten people or less. Therefore, when considering that there currently exist no incentives to employ apprentices in Ireland, macro-level mechanisms should be implemented whereby those employers willing to invest in VET are entitled to either fiscal rewards or taxation exemptions as an incentive to engage in training.

There are potential rewards for all stakeholders. At micro-level, the apprentice receives training, education and employment. At meso-level, the employer gains productivity and is socially responsible, a trait from which there are many benefits to exploit, not least of all in terms of industry promotion. At exo-level, the educational facilities are further engaged in didactic activity. But most importantly, at macro-level the state receives possibly the greatest benefit of all. In Ireland, apprentices are immediately classified as employees and not as students. Therefore, those individuals who gain employment via apprenticeship are productive to society, industry and the economy. Furthermore, as many apprentices would otherwise potentially fall into the category of NEETs, VET training removes them from placing a social welfare burden upon the state in the form of unemployment benefit.

Additionally, there is a need for a paradigm shift in the delivery of VET regarding employer engagement. Traditionally, an employer undertook to train apprentices within his/her firm for the duration of the apprenticeship, relatively confident in the firm's ability to deliver the necessary training due to an adequate supply of work. Today, however, that confidence is lacking, and firms appear unwilling to invest in VET due to the onerous obligations involved by being an employer. This is exacerbated by the fact that the vast majority (>90%) of construction industry employers are micro-firms, employing less than 10 people. Moreover, most of these micro-firms are sole-traders. Since the industry is built upon such micro-firms, these are the potential employers who should be the target of incentivization by the state regarding VET engagement.

As discussed via the associated presentation to the above paper, a large cohort (39%) of employers are undecided regarding their future involvement in training apprentices. It is reasonable to surmise that there are employers within this group who would potentially engage in training but are discouraged by the associated obligations discussed above. As these firms are likely to be in the category of micro-firms already mentioned, it is possible that a significant deterrent to their engagement in training is an uncertainty regarding the availability of sufficient work to support the employment of an apprentice.

Therefore, the above-mentioned paradigm shift is for employers to engage in shared apprenticeship training. The benefits are numerous. Apart from an obvious increase in apprenticeship training numbers, the micro-firm employers could deliver training in a smaller range of work-type and specialization, with the apprentice receiving the full range of requisite work-based learning from the larger co-operative of employers. Furthermore, the onerous obligations involved in being an employer would be significantly reduced when the responsibilities are shared, yet each firm still benefits from the associated productivity of an additional employee.

By exploring such possible interventions in apprenticeship engagement, employers can experience tangible benefits to the firm through VET. As discussed, apprenticeship training via

the natural skills cycle does not only deliver greater productivity but also proactively prepares the firm for future management skills requirements. As such, engaged employers can greatly increase the capacity of the industry to meet the needs of the economy and investors, future proof skills availability, and display great prudence and altruism via the social responsibility shown through employment of apprentices.

Olmos, Patricia, & Marhuenda, Fernando. (2019). The role of VET on the inclusion of marginalized young people and adult people from a lifelong perspective across the lifespan. In C. Nägele, M. Gessler, & B. E. Stalder (Eds.), *Vocational education and training across the lifespan. Report on the VETNET research workshop during the third EU Vocational Skills Week in Vienna, 07.11.2018* (pp. 42–48). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2653552>

The Role of VET on the Inclusion of Marginalized Young People and Adult People from a Lifelong Perspective across the Lifespan

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Abstract

In the current changing social, educational and labour contexts –where the transitions of marginalized young people and adult people from education into work and into adult life have become a difficult process– VET can develop a crucial role. Within a lifelong perspective across the lifespan, this work explores two areas around the role of VET where the perspective of inclusion in education and in the labour market as well as in adult social life can provide better knowledge in order to improve the quality of VET practices and policies. On the one hand, VET –in particular basic and/or initial VET– and on the other one, work based learning –in particular of VET perspective focused on how the social economy motto of putting people before profits is applied to the vocational qualification processes– are examples of ways in order to help young and adult marginalized people in their inclusion and hence contributing to citizenship.

Keywords

vocational education and training; inclusion; marginalized groups; lifelong learning; precariousness

Introduction

In September 2015 the UN published 17 sustainability goals that are designed to “end poverty, protect the planet and ensure prosperity for all” by 2030. Goal 4 focuses on education and calls for an ‘inclusive and quality’ provision for all.

VET can develop a crucial role on the achievement of this goal from a lifelong perspective across the lifespan, especially on the transitions from education into work and into adult work, in the current changing social, educational and labour contexts where such transitions have become a difficult process. This proposal explores two areas around VET role where the perspective of inclusion in education and in the labour market can provide better knowledge in order to improve the quality of VET practices and policies.

The first area is that of marginalized young people facing difficult transitions due to factors of vulnerability such as disability, unskilled profiles, or early school leaving situations, to name only a few. Normally, the lack of these personal resources and skills is one of the main reasons linked to their risk of being excluded (Schwartz, Côté & Jensen, 2005; Tagliabue et al., 2016; Thompson, Russell & Simmons, 2014). Against this background, education and training are considered key factors for providing young people with all those resources and skills that are required to cope with the demands of functioning effectively in these meaningful social, educational and labour contexts. VET –in particular basic and/or initial VET– is perceived as a strategic pathway, and alternative itinerary for tackling disadvantaged situation and improving

young people's opportunities for participating, hence contributing to their inclusion (CEDEFOP, 2016; European Commission, 2011; OECD, 2014; Olmos-Rueda & Mas-Torelló, 2013, Abiétar-López et al., 2017).

The second area deals with the inclusion of marginalized adult people through work based learning among others (accreditation of prior learning, access to VET, access to further education after completion of VET). Based upon two research projects³ conducted since 2007 in Spain (Marhuenda et al., 2010; Córdoba & Martínez, 2011; Chisvert et al., 2015; Marhuenda, 2016), VET perspective is focused on how the social economy motto of putting people before profits is applied to the vocational qualification processes of adults who have suffered long-term unemployment, single parents or migrant people, whose difficulties in adult life can be addressed through work and qualification in the vocational as well as in the personal and social domains, in order to help them out of poverty and social exclusion and hence contributing to citizenship (Marhuenda, 2017).

VET and marginalized young people's inclusion

Young people's inclusion in the current changing social, educational and labour contexts becomes a difficult process especially for all those young people facing difficult transitions due to factors related to vulnerable situations such as disability, unskilled profiles, early school leaving situations, to name only a few. Normally, the lack of these young people's personal resources and skills is one of the main argued reasons linked to their risk of being excluded from these (Schwartz, Côté, & Jensen, 2005; Tagliabue et al., 2016; Thompson, Russell, & Simmons, 2014). This mistrust is worse for disabled young people –especially for intellectual disabled young people– due to common misconception of the society and the workforce about their strengths, capacities and competencies for coping with the skills and levels of qualification and mediating concepts that are required by social, educational and labour contexts –see, for example, initiative, self-reliance, or adaptability, to name a few–. Regarding this misconception of disability, it is worth catching here the conception of disability of authors such as Hahn (1986, p. 128) or Oliver (1990, p. xiv), who state that disability emerges from the failure of a structured social setting when it has to adjust to disadvantaged citizens' needs and aspirations, rather than individuals' inability to adapt themselves to the demands of society.

Against this background, education and training –understood in terms of lifelong learning (LLL)– are considered key factors for providing young people with all those resources and skills that are required to cope with the demands of functioning effectively in these meaningful social, educational and labour contexts. VET –in particular basic and initial VET– is perceived as a strategic pathway, and alternative itinerary for tackling these young people's disadvantaged and vulnerable situation, and improving their opportunities for participating in these contexts, helping to their inclusion and social transformation. In other words, basic VET contribute to these young people's transitions, and support these vulnerable young people to become active citizens (Abiétar-López, Marhuenda-Fluixá, & Navas-Saurin, 2017; CEDEFOP, 2016; OECD, 2014; Olmos, 2013; Olmos-Rueda, 2017).

As it said before, through basic VET –and its respective programmes– young people can acquire basic skills and/or competencies that are key to getting their personal and social development and achieving educational and labour outcomes (CEDEFOP, 2011), and where educational and work agents play an important role. Tutors –as educational agents– and entrepreneurs –as work agents– have to work together, and with these youths, in the development of instrumental competencies –communicative, mathematical and digital competencies–, social and civic competencies, capacity of autonomy and initiative, learning to learn, emotional health –intrapersonal intelligence–, self-esteem, resilience, responsibility, punctuality, capacity for team working, or taking decisions, to give some of the most significant examples of basic VET

³ EDU2013-45919-R and SEJ2007-62145/EDUC

programmes provision addressed to vulnerable young people in terms of social, educational and labour inclusion (Olmos-Rueda & Mas-Torelló, 2017).

Basic VET programmes aim to work these basic skills and/or competencies, which are crucial for the improvement of young people's employability. Therefore, it is worth saying basic VET programmes –understood as a second chance to these youths at risk of exclusion that provide them with the opportunity of an educational and labour reintegration– have a positive impact on most of them, who get the educational support needed to achieve the education enabling them to be an acknowledged and productive members of society. However, according to some basic VET researches (Amores & Ritacco, 2016; Cedefop, 2016; Martínez-Carmona, Gil del Pino, & Álvarez-Castillo, 2016; Olmos & Mas, 2013; Mas, Olmos, & Salvà, 2017), some improvements are needed by these basic VET programmes. These improvements are linked to the adaptation of the strategies that are used for attending these young people's diversity – especially young people with disability, who are under-represented in basic VET programmes that do not have an adequate training offering, making difficult their access to the job market (Dincat, 2015)–, the improvement of teachers' pedagogical profile, the work for better young people's guidance processes in order to support their transitions, or the work with the families, the community, and other social, educational and work agents.

In the light of these results and reflections, it is needed to continue working on VET pathways for making these a really alternative for the educational, social and labour inclusion of this vulnerable group, all those young people who facing difficult transitions due to factors that are mainly related to unskilled profiles, and usually are linked to disabled condition and early school leaving situations.

Can VET play a role in the successful inclusion of adult people at risk of social exclusion?

For more than half a century in Western Europe, employment relations have been at the core of adult life. Being an adult consisted in having employment, being occupied, working for an employer or running your own business. Adulthood was related to your position in the world of work, submitted to its hierarchies, related to the wages related to those positions. Such positions were understood as the fruit of one's education, under the assumption that an specialized occupational or professional education (vocational education and training) would bring you to a certain position in society, based upon merit and professional accredited knowledge.

The agreement between capital and work, employers and employees, was the basis for the welfare state that Europe experienced between the end of the II World War and the turn of the century. Such agreement and relation, as the ILO (2016) has shown, has shifted towards an increase of what has been named 'non-standard forms of employment', 'precariousness' (Standing, 2011), or 'the working poor' (Shipler, 2005), to name a few. Employment relations have become loose and flexible, the labour market has experienced increased deregulation in some European countries (Cosubiela & Rojo, 2012), and the nature and role of work is changing in a large scale.

Vocational education and training was developed and built under the industrial idea of work and the employment relations where qualification played a relevant role, and if those notions are being questioned nowadays, there is good ground for calling a conference like SFIVET has done, 'the end of VET as we know it?'⁴. Can we conceive of vocational education without safe and long-term employment relations? Can we think of VET without a career perspective, where one's qualification are increased and evolve along the lifespan? Can we think of VET when unemployment rates are very high (Sanchis, 2016) or in relation to minijobs? If the panorama of work and its development is changing into unknown directions, does it still keep all of its

⁴ 6th Congress on Research on Vocational Education and Training in Switzerland, <https://www.sfivet.swiss/vet-congress-2019>

different values (Budd, 2014) and meanings along recent history (Díez, 2014); or do we have to start thinking of its devastation (Ovejero, 2014)?

The relevance of these questions is much greater if we think them in relation to adult people who are at risk of social exclusion for not being able to join the labour market and therefore being kept away from most of the ordinary relations in adult life. Among these, we can find unemployed adults, adult people with disabilities, adult people with mental health illnesses, adult people after long periods of addictions or of imprisonment, migrant adults whose qualifications and skills are not recognized.

For most companies, these people are seen as part of a disposable workforce and there is mistrust against them in recruiting practices, as well as considerably less options for upskilling offers and VET of any kind. They are often considered mainly a subject of social policy rather than of labour policy, and it is often the case that active employment policies addressed to these populations play more of a social role than a qualifying one.

However, the social economy (Monzón & Chaves, 2017) is able to put the person before the profit and to give work a social value, not just an instrumental one, by which employees show their skills and knowledge, contribute to production processes and the benefits are not just individual but also regional, in terms of social development.

The social economy shows that investing in people provides returns to the companies, and considers VET as part of that investment, and there are several examples of these around Spain ([Faedei](#), [Gureak](#), [Lantegi Batuak](#), [Proyecto Trèvol](#), [Aeress](#) or the [Asociación Española de Escuelas de Segunda Oportunidad](#)). In most of them, there are examples of intersection of VET with special education, intercultural education and adult education. In several of them there is preparation for work and for employment and citizenship, practices to increase the employability and sometimes even entrepreneurship, but with a clear purpose on the inclusion of adult people who have suffered in their lives back into the labour market as independent citizens.

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Minutes

The role of VET and social inclusion was the fourth and last impetus presentation to the research community participating in the meeting. This allowed us presenters to realize that the previous three presentations had addressed already questions relevant to social inclusion, as follows:

1. Societal eco-systems:
 - Stakeholders and VET providers establish a bidirectional relation, it is not just that VET providers have to be responsive to the needs of the labour market, the labour market can be inclusive and incorporate well trained and educated people no matter what record of past exclusion or vulnerability
 - If inclusion is a goal, it has to be a common one, shared by employers in order to make it effective. If inclusion is not a goal for them, they will not cooperate and efforts made by VET providers will be useless
 - Trust between sectors and actors may also foster the will to facilitate social inclusion, giving trainees a chance to show their abilities
 - Transition between life phases, stages and spheres is harder for those in need of support for social inclusion, but it is their right to, if they have been able to accomplish a VET qualification, which gives proof of their skills
 - Lifelong learning is today an obligation behind other notions like second chance or fostering employability
 - A prospective approach to vocational guidance should take into account social inclusion

2. Apprenticeship reform:
 - Freedom to choose your professional pathway demands conditions to make it available, and this is at stake for people at risk of social exclusion
 - Insofar apprenticeships entail the features of ordinary precarious employment, so they might be a good preparation for the current working chances and conditions, is this the kind of vocational preparation we are looking for?
 - Social inclusion after VET is not only a matter for large companies, but also for small and medium ones; and this demands support measures
 - Social responsibility in apprenticeships is necessary for the recognition of qualifications is expected, not just a market-driven preparation for a job; qualifications demand standardization and decent working and learning conditions
 - The liberalization of VET and apprenticeships in several countries has not proved inclusive

3. VET cycle:
 - The prospect of a career from apprentice to manager is appealing in terms of social inclusion, for it allows people to follow their expectations of progress
 - Access to further education along the lifespan is key to assure inclusion not only at

- work but also in terms of increasing one's qualification
- Trainers in apprenticeship schemes need training themselves, also in terms of promoting inclusion practices in the apprenticeships
- The emphasis on transversal skills favours social inclusion, as most of these skills are relevant not only for work but also for life purposes
- Social inclusion approaches warn us about too narrow approaches to VET at the lowest levels of qualification, encouraging people to upskill and promote in terms of a career instead of just finding a job
- Work based learning has long been considered a facilitator of social inclusion, for it provides a different approach to traditional academic learning

To add on these, we summarize here the main topics raised and discussed along the session:

- Focusing on marginalized groups runs the risk of stereotyping marginalization, and this should be avoided
- Skills monitoring and career guidance would help school to work transition for people at risk
- Entrepreneurship education in VET to reduce the risks of disadvantaged youth has not proved a successful alternative in the past. However, entrepreneurship as a competence is a goal that is valuable for all, not being limited to setting up own business
- Flexibility in training provision is a key to facilitate social inclusion, universal design of courses let learners approach their learning at a pace that recognises their different learning needs
- Broad vocational profiles, transversal skills and work process learning approaches facilitate a broad and inclusive career perspective
- Personalization of training and pathways by teachers and trainers suits the needs of people with disabilities, with a 'no-one-size-fits-all' approach; even if it has a higher cost it is conducive to higher quality and effectiveness for all
- New technologies should be used to facilitate learning to people with special needs
- The current context of increasing precarious pathways, zero-hour contracts, crowd-sourcing ... endangers people
- A focus on transversal skills and intrapersonal skills should be highlighted in curriculum design
- Good practices and data from them should be used to persuade employers to introduce inclusion in their policies, we should make visible those successful experiences
- Inclusive systems are often internally exclusive; is it possible to have a VET system inclusive when it is preparing for a selective labour market?
- We must address the confrontation between high quality and high inclusion
- Learning to learn is at the core of a perspective of social inclusion, with a focus upon transversal skills
- Cooperation with employers is necessary if social inclusion after VET is a goal
- Is VET the best educational chance to assure inclusion of marginalized young people? The working logic is not precisely inclusive
- Is VET able to cope with social policy as well as with economic promotion? Are both compatible?
- Inclusion (social, educational, work inclusion) is a condition of quality. To talk about VET quality and quality VET pathways requires taking into consideration the need of working on marginalized (vulnerable) young people's inclusion. It is key a definition of quality compatible with inclusion.